

DELIVERABLE REPORT

A HIGH-PRESSURE GAS TPC PROTOTYPE WITH HYBRID CHARGE-OPTICAL READOUT

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Abstract:

A high-pressure gas Time Projection Chamber (TPC) with optical readout and a hydrogen-rich gas mixture has the potential to provide the most precise measurement of neutrino interactions on nuclei. An R&D study for developing such a prototype could inform the design of a highly capable near detector for future neutrino experiments like DUNE. The Warwick TPC (WarTPC) serves as an R&D platform for readout technology and gas mixture development in high-pressure gas TPCs. It features a hybrid charge and optical readout, utilizing a TimePix3 camera for optical detection and two Thick Gas Electron Multipliers (THGEMs) for charge and light amplification. We have conducted measurements with various argon-CH₄ mixtures at 1 bar and with pure argon at pressures up to 6 bar. In this report, we present the prototype and discuss the observed effects of CH₄ quenching on argon VUV scintillation light, as well as the suppression of VUV light production at high pressures.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2025

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1 INTRODUCTION

The DUNE Phase 2 [1] Near Detector may include a high-pressure gas TPC operating with an argon-based gas mixture at 10 bar. One advantage of optical readout with cameras is its cost-effective scalability [5] compared to conventional charge readout, where each channel requires dedicated electronics. Additionally, camera readout offers unprecedented granularity. Therefore, identifying a gas mixture that enables both charge and optical readout is of interest [2].

Furthermore, if a hydrogen-rich gas mixture with good tracking properties can be identified, the Transverse Kinematic Imbalance (TKI) technique could be used to extract neutrino-hydrogen interactions event by event [3]. This would enable a nuclear-effect-free determination of the neutrino flux [3,4]. The superior spatial resolution of optical readout could provide the precise tracking required for TKI.

The Warwick Time Projection Chamber (WarTPC) serves as an R&D platform for readout technology and gas mixture development in high-pressure gas TPCs. In this report, we describe the WarTPC and present our first study using both optical and charge readout with a hydrogen-rich gas mixture, as well as high-pressure argon.

2 THE WARWICK TIME PROJECTION CHAMBER

WarTPC consists of a pressure vessel, a gas system, a TPC, an optical readout system, electronics, a monitoring system, a charge readout system, and a source holder.

2.1 Pressure Vessel

Fig. 1. The closed pressure vessel seen from the cathode side (left) and the camera side (right).

The pressure vessel is the biggest component of WarTPC. It is a 1-metre-long cylindrical chamber, 50 cm in diameter, and has a capacity of 195 litres with a maximum operating pressure of 10 bars (Fig. 1). It is mounted horizontally and bolted to a table. On each side, there is a door hinged with a

Davit arm on the vessel body; one of them has a view port for the light, hence referred to as the ‘camera side’. The other side is referred to as the ‘cathode side’ because the TPC cathode (see Sec. 2.3) is closer to it. Our design of the vessel (Fig. 2) has been inherited and adapted by other groups.

Fig. 2. The WarTPC pressure vessel CAD design.

2.2 Gas System

Fig. 3. Left: the gas outflow line (blue tube) and the inflow (which is connected to the gas cabinet in the background). Right: the sampling system with the pump disconnected, but valve attached, as well as the pressure gauge and RGA.

The gas system consists of three main parts: gas inflow, gas outflow, and sampling system (Figs. 3 and 4). The gas inflow connects the vessel with gas cylinders inside of a cabinet at the lab corner. Currently two gas cylinders can be connected. There are two check-valves to ensure that there is no

gas flow from one cylinder to another, as well as a valve before the line connecting to the vessel to allow for fine control. The gas outflow line connects the pressure vessel to the sampling system and the venting line that allows the contents of the vessel to be vented to atmosphere.

The sampling system can sample gas from both, the vessel and the gas cylinders. A three-way-valve is used to sample from both, without the risk of accidentally allowing gas flow between the inflow and outflow line. The sampling system is connected to a Residual Gas Analyser (RGA) which has a maximum operating pressure of 2 bar. Since the vessel is capable of operating at 10 bar, a large cylindrical volume is connected after the three-way-valve. This is to ensure that before the gas reaches the rest of the sampling system, the pressure drops as the gas expands to fill the volume. After this cylinder, there is a four-way-union that connects to a pump, pressure sensor, and the RGA. The pump is connected to the system via a valve which allows the rate of evacuation to be controlled (or shut off completely if need be). The pressure sensor is a PSG550 Pirani pressure gauge.

Fig. 4. Schematic for the WarTPC gas system.

2.3 TPC

The TPC's Field Cage (FC) (Figs. 5 and 6) consists of 17 steel rings and the cathode – all connected by a resistor chain – and has a drift length of approximately 42 cm. The cathode and FC rings have an outer diameter of 360 mm, and the ring shave an inner diameter of 260 mm and a pitch between each ring of 21.8 mm. The FC and cathode are supported by Delrin spacers (Fig. 7) that serve two purposes, firstly to provide structural support to the whole TPC, and secondly to ensure that the space between the cathode and field cage rings are as uniform as possible. The detector rests on two holders that are Delrin rods with equidistant 3 mm slits cut into them. The slits are spaced such that the pitch matches the pitch of the steel ring which can slot into them.

Fig.5. The field cage seen from the side (top), from the THGEM side (bottom left), and from the cathode side (bottom right).

Fig. 6. The CAD model of the filed cage seen from the side (left) and from the front (right)

Fig. 7. CAD model of the Delrin Spacer
seen from the side.

Two Thick Gas Electron Multipliers (THGEMs) are mounted to the FC along with a Wavelength Shifter (WLS). These THGEMs are 180 mm in diameter with 1 mm thickness. The THGEM hole diameter is 50 μm , with a pitch of 80 μm . The dielectric material is PCB with the electrodes being made of passivated copper. The WLS is made from a 2 mm thick 200 mm diameter borosilicate glass disc with a thin film of PEN (PolyEthylene Naphthalate) foil glued to it using an optically transparent epoxy. The WLS and the THGEMs have their own holders which can be mounted to the camera end of the field cage. When mounted, we distinguish the THGEM electrodes as “Top Of the Top” (TOT), and “Bottom Of the Top” (BOT) for the top THGEM, and “Top Of the Bottom” (TOB), and “Bottom Of the Bottom” (BOB) for the bottom THGEM. Using this naming scheme, the bottom THGEM is facing the drift volume, where the BOB electrode is closest to the field cage, and the top THGEM is the subsequent THGEM, where the TOT electrode is closest to the WLS.

2.4 Optical Readout

To achieve optical readout, a TimePix3 (TPX3) camera (Fig. 8) is used. The data produced by the TPX3 camera is naturally zero suppressed and can measure the Time-of-Arrival and the Time-over-Threshold (ToT) of light arriving at the chip [5,6], and has found use in other optical [5] and liquid [7] TPCs. It is a clear improvement over early attempts at high pressure gas TPC optical readout with e.g. CCD cameras [8]. A Photonis cricket image intensifier is used to amplify the image before it is read by the TPX3 camera. This image intensifier works by converting the incoming light into electrons via a photocathode. These electrons are then multiplied using a Micro-Channel Plate (MCP), before these electrons impinge on a phosphor screen, converting the electrons back into photons [7]. A camera mount is set up on a table to ensure that the camera is leveled and is held in place while at the viewport. The aforementioned zero suppressed readout, the TPX3's time resolution of ~ 1.6 ns, as well as its high sensitivity when combined with an image intensifier, make it one of the best suited devices for optical readout TPCs. We have commissioned the camera with the WarTPC over various runs with an alpha source (Sec. 2.6) and pure argon.

Fig. 8. TPX3 in mounted onto the camera mount.

2.5 Electronics, Monitoring, and Charge Readout

The cathode and THGEMs both have their own power supplies (Fig. 9 left). The cathode is powered by a two channel Caen N570 15 kV power supply, and the THGEMs are powered by a four channel Caen NDT1471H 5 kV power supply. Currently, the maximum drift field achievable with this setup

is ~ 313 V/cm. Two of the THGEM electrodes (Fig. 10) are connected to a Cremat CR-110 R2.2 preamplifier (Fig. 9, right) which is in turn mounted onto a CR-150 R6 evaluation board. The preamplifier decouples the AC charge signals from the power supply line; the corresponding amplifier internal circuit is rated to 2000 V, constraining the voltage difference between the two electrodes of the THGEM to maximal ~ 1900 V.

Note that we can decouple the charge signal from the two GEM electrodes. Furthermore there is the option of installing an anode and reading it through a dedicated feed-through. On the other hand, we currently lack a digitiser to properly record and process the signals. The preamplifier signal is only fed to an oscilloscope, allowing to see signals of the charge readout (Figs. 9 right and 10). Together with the TPX3 camera readout, simultaneous optical and charge readout is demonstrated, nonetheless.

The vessel's pressure sensor is a WIKA A-10 pressure sensor with a range from 0 to 16 bar. It is powered by a DC power supply. The temperature sensor is a PT100 temperature probe. Both the temperature probe and pressure sensor are connected to a DAQ to allow for recording and display of the ambient pressure and temperature.

Fig. 9. The two high voltage power supplies (left), and the preamplifier and evaluation board (right).

2.6 Source and Holder

A 3 kBq Am-241 alpha source is used as the ionisation source for this setup. It is held inside the drift volume by a holder (Fig. 11) which can be mounted between two field cage rings. It consists of three parts; the hook, the tray, and the grate. The tray houses the source, and has a depression cut into it to hold the source in place. The grate provides some protection to the source, as it prevents objects from coming in contact with it, and it also collimates the source to 1.5kBq. The grate is attached to the tray with nylon screws which screw into the bottom of the tray. The hook is used to mount the assembly onto the field cage.

Fig. 10. Circuit diagram for the THGEMs and charge readout.

Fig. 11. The disassembled source holder (left) showing the grate, hook, and tray, from left to right. The fully assembled holder is shown on the right.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Both the charge and optical readouts were tested using an alpha source, which was mounted inside the vessel, in various argon-methane mixtures. The test began with a CH_4 fraction of 0% (i.e. pure argon) and were repeated in 0.5% increments up to a final fraction of 10%. At every reading the cathode and THGEM settings were kept the same (5 kV cathode, -900 V BOB, 100 V TOB, 200 V BOT, 1100 V TOT). These settings were chosen after testing the THGEM stability. They provided a

good light signal. While it was possible to perform this test at settings that would provide a greater potential difference between each electrode (and thus greater amplification), these settings would be less stable.

For optical readout, the TPX3 camera was set up to record 600 frames of ToT data with each having an exposure time of 1 second. These frames were then integrated to obtain the final ToT integral signal. The charge readout was also monitored. Originally, it was planned to take a pulse height spectrum at each methane fraction. However, due to noise and the lack of a digitiser, only a baseline reading was performed and then at every CH₄ fraction, the charge readout was monitored for coincident events.

The initial purity of the argon was measured to be at least 99.8% at 1238 mbar. The aim was to achieve the highest possible argon purity. However, due to issues with the leak tightness of the sampling system, there is some background air that manages to seep into the sampling system. During the measurements taken at a methane fraction of 10%, the pressure was recorded at 1335 mbar. Initially, the RGA was used to measure the gas purity. However, while measuring the gas mixture with a fraction of methane in, it was discovered that the RGA was not calibrated correctly. Instead, the initial pressure was recorded, and then pure (>99.99%) methane was added until the vessel reached a target pressure which would give us the desired methane fraction.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Methane Measurement

Below are the integrated light images for different methane fractions (Fig. 12), as well a collection of coincident events recorded with the charge readout (Fig. 13). There is a clear drop off in the amount of light collected, as expected.

Due to the steep drop off between 0% and 0.5% methane, this can be better illustrated when moving to a 1D representation of the 2D ToT signal images (Fig. 14). This was done by fitting a 2D histogram to the integrated image data and then discarding everything outside the ± 1 sigma y range. This was then projected onto the x-axis producing a Gaussian distribution. A simple Gaussian distribution plus a polynomial was used to fit the signal and background. The background was subtracted, and then the total Time-over-Threshold was calculated from the remaining gaussian.

Fig. 13. Coincident events recorded at various methane fractions.

Fig. 14. The raw data fit with a 2D gaussian (top). The resulting background + gaussian are slicing the data (bottom).

This was then repeated for each CH₄ fraction. The relative optical signal strength was calculated by taking the ToT integral of the signal at 0% CH₄, and using that to divide the ToT integral at each CH₄ fraction. The results can be seen in Fig. 15 and Table 1 in the Appendix. As can be seen, there is an incredibly sharp drop off with even 0.5% methane added, which then slows down considerably.

Fig. 15. Calculated relative optical signal strength as a function of the CH₄ fraction.

Throughout the test, coincident signals (i.e. charge signals seen in both channel 1 and channel 2) were seen at all methane fractions. Considering that no such coincident events were observed when the field and THGEMs were not biased (as described in Sec. 3), this is a very promising sign. However, it should be noted that, without being able to produce a pulse height spectrum, this cannot be claimed definitively.

As mentioned previously in Sec. 3, a pulse height spectrum was taken “by hand” for the CH₄ fraction of 0%. However, due to noise in the readings (some of this noise can be seen in Fig. 11. where there seems to be sharp spikes throughout the waveforms) and not having this process automated, this was difficult and very time consuming. In the end, 20 events were recorded. Channel 1 was connected to the BOB electrode (i.e. the unamplified signal), and channel 2 was connected to the TOT (i.e. the amplified signal). The resulting spectrum can be seen in Fig. 16. While it is encouraging that the

signals in channel 1 are generally lower than those in channel 2, the statistically limited data set prevents drawing a definitive conclusion and instead underscores the need for further development.

Pulse Height Spectrum of Charge Readout Events

Fig. 16. Example Pulse height spectrum of channel 1 (left), and channel 2 (right) taken in an Ar-100, CH₄-0 gas mixture.

4.2 Argon Pressure Measurement

A similar measurement was repeated, but instead of adding methane, the effect of increasing the argon pressure on light readout was tested. As with the previous test, the settings were kept the same and the only change was the pressure of the argon gas. Starting at 1019 mbar, the pressure was increased in increments of 50 mbar until 1320 mbar. This was approximately the pressure range used in the methane test and serves as the baseline for comparing the effects of increasing the pressure. Afterwards, the pressure was increased to 1500 mbar, and then further increased by 500 mbar until a maximum pressure of 6000 mbar. Figure 19 is the graph of light output as a function of pressure.

Fig. 17. The integrated ToT images at different pressures of argon.

Fig. 18. Coincident events observed at different argon pressures.

Fig. 19. Calculated relative optical signal strength as a function of the argon pressure.

As can be seen in Fig.17, there is a clear drop off in light as the pressure increases. This is more noticeable at higher pressures but can be seen more clearly in Fig. 19 and also Table 2 in the Appendix. There is an initial steep drop followed by a slower drop.

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The WarTPC was commissioned with a TimePix3 camera-based optical readout and a charge readout, which decoupled the induced signals on two of the TPC's THGEM electrodes. Both readout methods performed as expected, demonstrating that our prototype can serve as a testbed for hybrid-readout high pressure gas TPC technology.

In the report, the entire WarTPC system underwent its first measurements with a hydrogen-rich gas mixture and a hybrid optical-charge readout. The optical readout performed as expected, with the ToT integrated signal decreasing as the CH₄ fraction increased. The charge readout, however, was significantly impacted by the absence of digitization, though it showed promising signs, as coincident events were observed across all CH₄ fractions. During tests with increasing argon pressure, the ToT integrated signal generally decreased as expected, while coincident charge readout events remained observable at all pressures.

One limitation of this measurement is that, due to the absence of a digitiser, pulse height spectra could not be recorded, except for the 0% CH₄ fraction measurement. Further work is needed to enable the recording of these spectra. The first step, after implementing digitisation, would be to filter out noise from the power supplies, as they appear to be a significant source of interference. Once this is achieved, automating the measurement process should be explored to facilitate the recording of a larger number of events. Additionally, using preamplifiers with a lower output voltage per pC of charge may be beneficial, as some events already show nearly saturated or fully saturated preamplifier output (see Figs. 13 and 18). Another limitation is the tightness of the sampling system, which may be affecting gas purity readings (Sec. 3) and requires further investigation. Currently, a vacuum of 0.1 mbar is achieved, which is sufficient for accurate gas mixture readings.

It should also be noted that as pressure increases, the THGEMs and field cage can be biased to progressively higher voltages. However, the THGEMs are limited by the voltage tolerance of the preamplifiers (2000 V). To overcome this limitation, alternative solutions such as new evaluation boards may be required. Otherwise, the preamplifiers' voltage tolerance would become the limiting factor for THGEM biasing and, consequently, the amount of light produced at higher pressures.

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8 APPENDIX

Pressure (mbar)	Methane Fraction (%)	Calculated ToT Integral (ns)	Error (ns)	Relative Strength (%)	Error on Relative Signal Strength (%)
1231	0	252000000	2000000	100.0	-
1218	0.5	70000000	1000000	27.8	0.5
1225	1.1	62000000	1000000	24.7	0.5
1224	1.5	54000000	1000000	21.7	0.5
1232	2	42000000	1000000	16.8	0.4
1239	2.5	36700000	900000	14.6	0.4
1249	3	35200000	900000	13.9	0.4
1258	3.6	30000000	1000000	12.0	0.4
1264	4	28000000	1000000	11.3	0.4
1272	4.5	22700000	800000	9.0	0.3
1278	5.0	24000000	900000	9.5	0.4
1279	5.5	16900000	900000	6.7	0.3
1287	6.0	14500000	800000	5.7	0.3
1294	6.5	14500000	800000	5.8	0.3
1301	7.0	12800000	600000	5.1	0.3
1309	7.6	12800000	800000	5.1	0.3
1314	8.0	13400000	900000	5.3	0.3
1314	8.5	14000000	800000	5.6	0.3
1319	9.0	13200000	700000	5.2	0.3
1327	9.5	11400000	700000	4.6	0.3
1335	10.0	11200000	800000	4.4	0.3

Table 1. The calculated optical ToT integral with its associated errors, and the relative signal strength in percent as a function of methane fraction.

Pressure (mbar)	Calculated ToT Integral (ns)	Error (ns)	Relative Strength (%)	Error on Relative Signal Strength (%)
1019	411000000	2000000	100	-
1070	182000000	2000000	44.37	0.01
1120	164000000	2000000	39.97	0.01
1170	210000000	2000000	51.05	0.01
1222	208000000	2000000	50.57	0.01
1270	193000000	2000000	47.05	0.01
1320	178000000	1000000	43.20	0.01
1500	149000000	1000000	36.31	0.01
2000	132200000	900000	32.16	0.01
2503	103000000	1000000	24.95	0.01
3000	97000000	1000000	23.67	0.01
3500	79000000	1000000	19.14	0.01
4000	63000000	1000000	15.23	0.01
4500	44300000	800000	10.77	0.01
5000	34700000	900000	8.43	0.01
5500	25700000	800000	6.24	0.01
6000	19000000	800000	4.62	0.01

Table 2. The calculated optical ToT integral with its associated errors, and the relative signal strength in percent as a function of argon pressure.